

PROCEDIN

Building Procurement Capability for Embedding and Driving Innovation

D3.2

In-person trainings and recorded legal trainings

Progress Report

March 2024

Funded by
the European Union

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Work Package	WP3
Delivery Date (DoA)	31/03/2024
Actual Delivery Date	21/02/2024

Document Revision History			
Date	Version	Author/Contributor/Reviewer	Summary of Main Changes
20/12/2023	0.1	HAA	First draft
10/01/2024	0.2	HAA / F65, GAB	Second draft to consortium with feedback incorporated
15/01/2024	0.3	HAA / F65, GAB, UT	Third draft to consortium with feedback incorporated. Adjustments made to lay-out
01/02/2024	0.4	HAA / F65, GAB, UT, Pedal	Internal review
14/03/2024	1.0	HAA / F6S, GAB, UT, Pedal	Final version

Dissemination Level and Nature of the Deliverable		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Nature	R = Report, E = Ethics or, O = Other	R

PROCEDIN Consortium			
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PROCEDIN

Procurement Capability - Embedding and Driving Innovation

Grant Agreement: 101070830

Funding Scheme: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)

Theme: HORIZON-EIE-2021-CONNECT-01

Start Date of Project: 01 October 2022

Duration: 24 months

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	5
2	The Training Sessions	5
2.1	Background	5
2.2	The Set-Up.....	6
2.3	Distribution of the Training Sessions	11
3	Conclusion.....	12
3.1	Next Steps	12
4	Appendices.....	13

List of Figures

Figure 1: Modules of the E-Learning of UA IRPP.....	6
Figure 2: First slide of one of the legal framework training sessions	7
Figure 3: Coordinator of the Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement, Valentina Schippers-Opejko presenting one of the LF trainings	8
Figure 4: The first and third legal framework training sessions were held in the council chamber of the Municipality of Haarlem	8
Figure 5: Pre-Commercial Procurement Step-by-Step Guide	
Figure 6: Case Example Accompanying the Procedure of Pre-Commercial Procurement	
Figure 7: Specific Step of the Procedure Accompanied by a Substantive Example.....	10
Figure 8: Example of an Exercise Used in the Pre-Commercial Procurement Training	11
Figure 9: Videos of the Training Sessions Uploaded to the PROCEDIN Resource Bank.....	

List of Tables

Table 1 Overview Training Sessions & Topics	Error! Bookmark not defined.
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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
UA IRPP	Urban Agenda on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement
POI	Procurement of Innovation

1 Introduction

The core goals of the PROCEDIN project are to build leadership capacity for driving and embedding innovation and to accelerate the uptake of procurement of innovation (POI) through guidance and resources for buyers and vendors. Training programs are key to the transformative process of promoting POI practices. They can serve as a foundation that enables individuals and teams to not only understand but also actively adopt innovative procurement practices. In the dynamic field of procurement, where technologies, the market, and the regulatory landscapes continually change and evolve, training sessions provide an up-to-date and instructive form of guidance. By providing education on the latest trends, methodologies, and technological advancements, training equips procurement professionals with the knowledge and skills needed to identify, evaluate, and implement innovative solutions. Moreover, it fosters collaborative thinking toward continuous improvement and creativity to navigate the challenges that come with procurement of innovation.

This progress report provides a detailed account of the advancements made in PROCEDIN's ongoing training initiatives.

2 The Training Sessions

2.1 Background

In line with the Grant Agreement, the partners of the PROCEDIN consortium have been organising four two-day training sessions on the legal framework of innovation procurement. The choice to organise two-day meetings is based on achieving more efficiency of learning rather than one-day training. In two days, more legal aspects can be addressed and more in-depth topics can be included in the training, resulting in better knowledge outcomes. In-person training sessions also tend to have a better impact and results and provide better possibilities for interaction and exercises.

For the previous Deliverable, D3.1, PROCEDIN advanced and developed training materials in collaboration with the Urban Agenda Partnership for Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement (UA IRPP). To further enhance the resources already designed and launched by the UA IRPP partnership has been a deliberate decision to stimulate collaboration and co-creation and to guarantee quality and ease of access. This is in line with the premise of leveraging existing strengths and promoting new links.

For this Deliverable, D3.2 *In-person trainings and recorded legal trainings*, PROCEDIN builds both on this premise as in D3.1, by using the developed training materials in the in-person training sessions and the UA IRPP meetings to organise the training sessions. The UA IRPP has a lot of experience in organising and delivering such training sessions and events. Through this collaboration, PROCEDIN keeps contributing to the promotion of the E-Learning module¹ developed by the UA IRPP, where the training materials have been published, while the UA IRPP provides PROCEDIN with access to the target groups that include procurers, legal procurement advisors, strategic procurement advisors, and sustainability and innovation procurement advisors. Participation in the training sessions is open to anyone interested, in addition to the UA IRPP network and partners.

¹ E-Learning modules Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement: <https://uapp.maester.com/>
This module presents a toolbox with different legal aspects in procurement of innovation.

2.2 The Set-Up

The training sessions aim to deliver legal assistance on the legal aspects of procurement of innovation. This [legal framework module](#) consists of several procedures and instruments. Therefore, the consortium decided to build the training sessions around these procedures and instruments.

Figure 1: Modules of the E-Learning of UA IRPP

The training modules follow the procurement cycle (see Figure 1) as they are presented in [the E-learning module](#), ranging from introductory knowledge to concrete and specific sessions on topics such as total cost of ownership. Table 1 lists the training sessions and their topics. The training sessions aim to provide European public authorities with legal support on the legal framework for procurement of innovation, thereby improving POI capacities. As mentioned in the grant agreement, KPI-3 assumes that at least 80 people receive direct training from PROCEDIN. Thanks to various promotion efforts, such as on social media, sharing of information in networks of the consortium partners, and reaching out through other channels, 137 people have already attended the training sessions on the legal framework in person and 20 people have attended the online webinar, while not even all the training sessions have taken place yet. In addition to this number of participants, another 40 people have watched the recorded trainings online (unique views).

Training sessions	Date	How/Where	Topic(s)	No. of attendants	No. unique online views of training sessions generated online /recorded training sessions
1st 2-day Training	May 22 nd & 23 rd 2023	During an in-person Urban Agenda Partnership Meeting, Haarlem, The Netherlands	Capacity building on innovative and circular procurement by public authorities	45	-

2nd 2-day Training	July 10 th & 11 th 2023	Mayors Covenant Municipality of Gabrovo, Bulgaria	Market Consultation	69	13
Extra Training	September 21 st 2023	Online webinar	Market Consultation	20	-
3rd 2-day Training	November 28 th & 29 th 2023	In-person Urban Agenda Partnership Meeting, Haarlem, The Netherlands	Competitive Dialogue, Pre-Commercial Procurement, Innovation Partnership	23	27
4th 2-day Training	April 10 th & 11 th 2024	In-person Urban Agenda Partnership Meeting, Haarlem, The Netherlands	Total Cost of Ownership, Award Below Threshold, Functional Specification, Human Centred Design	n/a	n/a
Extra Trainings	Before the end of June	Online webinar	Online workshops for SMEs and start-ups	n/a	n/a

Table 1: Overview Training Sessions & Topics

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Legal Framework Training: Competitive Dialogue

Valentina Schippers-Opejko
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In collaboration with:

URBAN AGENDA FOR THE EU

Figure 2: First slide of one of the legal framework training sessions

Figure 3: Coordinator of the Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement, Valentina Schippers-Opejko presenting one of the LF trainings

Figure 4: The first and third legal framework training sessions were held in the council chamber of the Municipality of Haarlem

The first training served as an introductory training set to the series of training sessions on capacity building with regard to the legal framework of innovative procurement. From there on, the training sessions dived into several legal procedures and instruments. For the second training, the partners of the consortium saw an opportunity to combine a training with the Mayor's Covenant of the Municipality of Gabrovo, Bulgaria, which was held in July 2023. This event had a broad outreach to our target groups. In collaboration with a Bulgarian translator, a training on market consultation has been provided. To make use of the designed training to the fullest, the partners decided to offer the same training also to the broader public. That is why an extra training was held as an online webinar, in addition to an online Urban Agenda Partnership meeting. The third set of training sessions covered

three procedures: Competitive Dialogue, Pre-Commercial Procurement, and Innovation Partnership. The fourth set of training sessions will be held in the upcoming Urban Agenda Partnership meeting in April 2024 and will cover four legal instruments: Total Cost of Ownership, Award Below Threshold, Functional Specification, and Human Centred Design. The training for SMEs and start-ups will be provided in online form to provide access to a broader group of participants. This online training for SMEs and start-ups will be provided at latest by June 2024. Figures 2, 3, and 4 give an impression of the in-person legal framework training sessions.

The training sessions on the legal framework have been designed to a specific structure. As mentioned, for each procedure and instrument PROCEDIN has developed a roadmap that defines important steps to take to complete the procedure or to successfully use the instrument. For the training sessions, each step is individually addressed and explained. The legal instrument or procedure that is central to the training is accompanied by a case example. This case example is split up along the different theoretical steps of the roadmap. Hence, in addition to elaborating on the step in the procedure/instrument, the same step in the case example is highlighted. This makes the theoretical subject matter more accessible and tangible. During in-person trainings, there is a possibility for questions and answers regarding the legal instruments and procedures. In this way, legal support can be provided to the public authorities, that participate in the in-person trainings.

Figure 5 displays a PowerPoint slide of the opening of the training by portraying an overview of the steps of the procedure that will be discussed step-by-step and Figure 6 displays a PowerPoint slide of the case example that accompanies the specific procedure, in this case, pre-commercial procurement.

Pre-Commercial Procurement A step-by-step guide

Figure 5: Pre-Commercial Procurement Step-by-Step Guide

Helsinki, Finland

Helsinki is participating in the AI4Cities-project, that helps cities to achieve their climate action commitments by applying the use of Artificial Intelligence.

AI4Cities-project tries to find carbon neutrality accelerating AI solutions with Pre-Commercial Procurement.

This case has been put forward by KEINO Competence Centre, Finland

Figure 6: Case Example Accompanying the Procedure of Pre-Commercial Procurement

Figure 6 portrays a PowerPoint slide that displays a specific step of the procedure accompanied by a substantive example of the step taken out of the case example as presented in Figure 5.

Identify the need of innovation

Case

Helsinki aims to achieve **carbon neutrality** by the year 2035. The majority of Helsinki's greenhouse gas emissions comes from **energy supply and transportation: 56% heating and 24% transport**.

Figure 7: Specific Step of the Procedure Accompanied by a Substantive Example

In addition to the explanation of the legal procedure/instrument and the illustration through examples, an exercise is added towards the end of the training. The use of exercises keeps the audience engaged and helps them actively internalize the information that has been provided to them. Figure 8 portrays a PowerPoint slide with one of the exercises that has been used in the training on pre-commercial procurement.

Exercise

Formulate your need in innovation as a challenge

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Figure 8: Example of an Exercise Used in the Pre-Commercial Procurement Training

2.3 Distribution of the Training sessions

The training sessions that have been organised and that will be organised in 2024 are mainly in-person training sessions. As discussed, this has been a deliberate choice. However, the consortium partners are well aware that not everyone has the opportunity to travel or to attend these training sessions in person. Therefore, all the training sessions have been recorded for distribution. The training sessions have also been uploaded to the resource bank on the PROCEDIN website² (Figure 6). This way, the training sessions are easily accessible to anyone who had to miss the in-person training or who would like to [rewatch the training](#).

Figure 9: Videos of the Training Sessions Uploaded to the PROCEDIN Resource Bank

² <https://procedin.eu>

3 Conclusion

Through the organisation of these training sessions on the legal framework of procurement of innovation, this deliverable, *In-person trainings and recorded legal trainings*, adds to the objectives of working package 3 by providing legal assistance and deploying the legal framework of innovation and innovative procurement. These training sessions serve as essential tools for understanding the legal framework surrounding innovative procurement practices. Several key points underscore the importance and value of these initiatives:

- **Stimulating Innovation:** Stakeholders are encouraged to explore innovative solutions. By making them aware of the legal aspect of innovative procurement, they will be able to explore this without fear of legal pitfalls, leading to better and quicker adoption of procurement of innovation.
- **Facilitating Collaboration:** The legal training sessions bring together diverse stakeholders, including legal professionals, procurement officers, and innovators. It adds to collaboration and learning from others by making use of existing knowledge that every individual holds.
- **Adaptability to Changing Regulations:** The legal landscape is dynamic, with regulations evolving over time. Training sessions include the most up-to-date information and help foster adaptability of organizations when regulations change to prevent their innovative initiatives are compromised.

3.1 Next Steps

To use the fullest potential of these training sessions, the following next steps will be undertaken:

- **The 4th two-day training sessions:** will be provided on the 10th and 11th of April 2024 in Haarlem, The Netherlands. Promotion of the training sessions has been set in motion already through the network of the UA IRPP and network of consortium partners of EU-funded PROCEDIN project and sister Horizon projects, e.g., BUILD. The training sessions will also be promoted through the use of social media, such as LinkedIn, and by handing out flyers during different conferences that the consortium partners attend in the coming weeks/months.
- **Promoting the PROCEDIN resource bank through the E-Learning module:** the E-Learning module contains a click-through to the resource bank of PROCEDIN, which will keep the resources produced by PROCEDIN, such as the recorded training sessions, circulated throughout different networks.
- **Continuously promoting the resource bank through networks and social media:** the consortium partners of PROCEDIN will continuously promote the resource bank of the PROCEDIN website, through social media, their professional networks, and conferences that they attend.
- **Extra trainings:** in the form of online workshops for SMEs and start-ups will be given through webinars before the end of June.

4 Appendices

Screenshot of the invitation mail for the fourth Legal Framework trainings

We herewith invite all partners and associates to join our meeting of the Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement. This meeting will be in person in Haarlem – the Netherlands.

During this meeting we will also organise PROCEDIN Legal Framework trainings on procurement instruments/processes:

On April 10th: Total Cost of Ownership & Direct Agreement
On April 11th: Functional Specification & Human Centred Design

We will be happy to welcome you on Wednesday **April 10** between 8:30 and 9:00 am for coffee/tea/registration and start our meeting at 9:00 am. In the evening we will organise an informal dinner for those who would like to join.

On **April 11** we will start at 9:00 and finish around 1:00 pm, with lunch for those who would like to attend. It is possible to extend the meeting for subgroup meetings in the afternoon, but this will be voluntarily if Action Groups need extra time.

The agenda will be disseminated closer to the meeting date.

Screenshot of the agenda for the upcoming Legal Framework trainings:

Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Public Procurement for EU Meeting on April 10th and 11th, 2024

Location: **City Hall Haarlem, Raadzaal, Grote Markt 2, Haarlem** (12 minutes walking from the Central Train Station of Haarlem)

Wednesday April 10

- 08:30-09:00 Welcome with coffee/tea
- 09:00-09:15 Kick off: Agenda and goals by UA Coordinator Valentina Schippers-Opejko & welcome by Saskia Havelaar, Manager Program & Area Department
- 09:15-09:30 Update on the EU funded project 'LIFE: Future Proof Sports Pitches' [by 2](#)
- 09:30-09:45 Update on the EU funded project 'PROTECT' [by 2](#)
- 09:45-10:00 Update on the EU funded project 'PROCEDIN' by Louise Knight (University of Twente)
- 10:00-10:15 Coffee/tea break
- 10:15-12:30 **Action Group 1:**
- 10:15-10:30 1. Presentation and Launch of the Urban Agenda Public Procurement Platform by José Navarro Gavilán and Conxita Francisco Brumos (Barcelona Provincial Council)
- 10:30-11:45 2. Position Paper 'Advocacy opportunities for the UA Partnership'
- 11:45-12:00 3. Decision about the expansion of the UA E-learning module with different languages (which ones?)
- 12:00-12:50 Lunch
- 12:50-13:10 **Action Group 3:**
Examples of Partners using Public Procurement to realise Economic Regeneration by Matthew Baqueriza-Jackson (URBACT)
- 13:10-14:00 Presentation 'Measuring Impact of Spend by using data-oriented procurement tools' by Stefan Rijter and Judith Strijk (Municipality of Amsterdam)
- 14:00-15:00 **PROCEDIN Legal Framework Training:
'Award Below Threshold & Total Cost of Ownership'**
- 15:00-15:20 Coffee/tea break
- 15:20-16:20 **PROCEDIN Legal Framework Training:
'Functional Specification & Human Centred Design'**

Banner to promote the fourth Legal Framework trainings

LEGAL FRAMEWORK TRAININGS

10 April 2024
14:00 - 15:00 CET
Award Below Threshold & Total Cost of Ownership

10 April 2024
15:20 - 16:20 CET
Functional Specification & Human Centred Design

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Scan to register!

JOIN US IN-PERSON AT:
Grote Markt 2, Haarlem
The Netherlands

Article on the PROCEDIN-website to promote the Legal Framework trainings:

Join PROCEDIN to Learn and Innovate in Public Procurement

Lilja Carvalho February 23, 2024

PROCEDIN
PROCEDIN free training sessions
Training 1: Award Below Threshold and Total Cost of Ownership
Training 2: Functional Specification and Human Centred Design
10 April 2024
14:00 - 18:20 CET
Municipality of Haarlem, The Netherlands
The registration is free, but the seats are limited.
LEARN MORE

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Public procurement is a vital sector that affects millions of people. It involves the acquisition of goods and services by public authorities to meet the needs of the society. However, public procurement also faces many challenges, which means that public procurement needs to embrace innovation so it can achieve better outcomes, such as efficiency, quality, sustainability, as well as foster economic growth and social progress.

But how can public procurement become more innovative? What are the tools and methods? And what are the best practices and examples?

This project's mission is to encourage the Procurement of Innovation capability development and accelerate the growth of Circular Economy and Green Mobility innovation ecosystems, and these are some of the questions that PROCEDIN aims to answer.

On **April 10th**, 2024, organized in the scope of PRODIN and embedded in the Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative & Responsible Public Procurement meeting, two training sessions will take place in Haarlem, the Netherlands: one on the topic **Award Below Threshold and Total Cost of Ownership** and another one about **Functional Specification and Human Centred Design**.

These training sessions will allow participants to learn about the legal framework and practical application of these topics, using real case examples and interactive exercises, while also offering a unique opportunity for networking and knowledge exchange.

PROCEDIN Project team invites all professionals and stakeholders involved in public procurement to participate in these highly informative and hands-on training sessions. The registration is free, but the seats are limited.

Don't miss this chance to unleash your innovative potential in public procurement!

Register now: PROCEDIN Legal Framework Training Sessions: Training 1: Award Below Threshold and Total Cost of Ownership & Training 2: Functional Specification and Human Centred Design

Search...

BUILD project: Free training on innovative procurement methods
28/02/2024

Health InnoFacilitator launches Coaching Services for Innovation Procurement
26/02/2024

Join PROCEDIN to Learn and Innovate in Public Procurement
23/02/2024

The Evolution of Innovation Procurement: Join the PROCEDIN Community – Express Your Interest by March 30!
25/01/2024

The Pivotal Role of SMEs in Driving Innovation in Procurement
17/01/2024